

Knowledge of diabetes, its complications of diabetes among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus

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Abstract:

Background:

Low knowledge about diabetes risk factors coupled with high disease prevalence is common in low-resource countries. Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) is quite prevalent in the world, with a proportion of 1 in every 300 persons and steadily rising frequency of incidence of about 3% every year. More alarmingly, the incidence of T1DM among infants is also increasing, with children as young as 6 months succumbing to it, instead of that at a rather established vulnerable age of around seven and near puberty, when the hormones antagonize the action of insulin. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) is the largest country in the Middle East that occupies approximately four-fifths of the Arabian Peninsula supporting a population of more than 33.3 million people, of whom 26% are under the age of 14 years. As per the Diabetes Atlas (8th edition). **Aim of the study:** This study aimed to measure the extent to which parent are Knowledge of diabetes, its complications and prevention diabetes among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus. **Method:** A cross sectional descriptive study was conducted at in Diabetic Center during Makkah City in September 2019 in Saudi Arabia, the estimated study sample size will be 500 parents of children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus during visiting the data collection period. Systematic random sampling technique is adopted. **Results:** our participants almost of parent (52.6%) were in the age group 40-60 and the data ranged from

(20.5-68) by mean $\pm$ SD(44.849 $\pm$ 12.035),the majority of them were males (74%) the education status that almost of respondents had university educational degree were

(59%). participant knowledge of information about knowledge about diabetes, complications, and ways to prevent diabetes of Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus in average. significant relation between knowledge about complications and demographic data were P-value=0.001.

Conclusion. The danger of late complications of diabetes increases with cumulative exposure to elevated blood glucose levels, and treatment that returns circulating glucose to near-normal levels protects against these long-term complications. The results reveal those parents are Knowledge of diabetes, its complications and prevention diabetes among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus inadequate.

Keywords: Knowledge, diabetes, complications, parents, children, Type1 mellitus.

Introduction:

Diabetes mellitus (DM) appears to be a global epidemic and an increasingly major non-communicable disease threatening both affluent and non-affluent society.[1] The study aimed to determine the knowledge of diabetic complications among diabetes mellitus patient visiting the Diabetic Center.[2]

Despite the widespread proposals and promotion in regards to fitting consideration for kids with diabetes , lacking diabetes parents Knowledge of diabetes, complications Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus information, principle among diabetes kids. In 2000, diabetes influenced an expected 171 million individuals around the world; by 2011 this had expanded to more than 366 million and numbers are required to surpass 552 million by 2030 [3]

The ordinary pervasiveness of DM (type 1) among Saudis is 0.23%, and the general predominance of type 2 is 0.12% between these under the age about 14 years.[4] Medical specialists emphatically accept that the real commonness of DM among kids and teenagers in the Saudi Arabia is a lots greater than up to expectation reported. For kids and young people, are significant areas for auxiliary counteraction mediations to assist them with limiting their

hazard for confusions related with DM . want for greater adaptability with respect to glucose checking and timing of food, a requirement for better dietary data in regards to cafeteria nourishments, and stress over diabetes crises at school were as yet revealed. [5]

Diabetes is a mind boggling disease charged by weakness to chronic complications confusions. The primary complications are macrovascular and microvascular complications. Advancement of Diabetes is related with expanded mortality and high danger of creating retinal, vascular and neuropathic intricacies prompting handicap and death.[6]

Parents may be able to influence the mentality and behavior of the younger by means of their insight. Inside the home they are additionally considered as the principle guardians to these kids. parents ' consciousness of medical issues could assume a role in mitigating the kid's experiencing diabetes and its inconveniences. [7]

The formative changes that happen as school kids with type 1 diabetes develop into youth require visit reevaluation of their restorative needs. Singular contrasts in caloric admission identified with development sprays and cooperation in sports, beginning of menses in female young people, and pre-adult emotional episodes are largely factors that families must consider in overseeing care and empowering self-care by through it youths.[8]

Diabetes mellitus sort one (DM1) markedly alters the lives of people and their families. Members of the family are can be affected by diabetes and its treatment, causing burden, distress, and reduced quality of life (QOL). There are in depth studies that judge the medical, social, and psychological impact of diabetes on children until yet not several discuss the malady and its direct impact on members of the family, and even fewer investigate the money problems in relation to diabetes and its oral complications .[9]

There are two forms of type 1 diabetes:

- Idiopathic type 1. This refers to rare forms of the disease with no known cause.
- Immune-mediated diabetes. An autoimmune disorder in which the body's immune system destroys. [10]

As the incidence of type 1 diabetes in children and adolescents will increase, it becomes progressively important to differentiate recently diagnosed type 1 from type 1diabetes. Within

the slender child, one can confidence assumes a designation of type 1 diabetes disorder. However, within the overweight adolescent, differentiating type 1 from type 2 diabetes may be difficult [11]

Diabetes has approximately registered a ten-fold increase in the past three eras in Saudi Arabia. Diabetes mellitus (DM) has been found to be related to high mortality, morbidity and vascular complications, accompanied by poor general health and lower quality of life. In Saudi Arabia, DM is quickly reaching disturbing proportions and becoming a significant cause of medical complications and even death.[12]

According to World Health Organization (WHO) in 2012, an estimated 1.5 million deaths were a direct outcome to diabetes and another 2.2 million deaths were attributively related to high blood glucose in a global population . As a consequence, researches confirmed that diabetics have a shorter life expectancy than non-diabetic individuals and this extravagant mortality is predominantly due to diabetic complications.[13]

Literature Review

Diabetes education is an essential tool to achieve treatment objectives in type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM). This study to measure was to determine if awareness diabetes in the parents and socio demographic factors affect Knowledge of diabetes, its complications among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus. Nobody knows without a doubt what causes type 1 diabetes, however researchers think it has something to do with genes. Genes for diabetes isn't usually enough. As a rule, a kid must be presented to something different — like an infection — to get type 1 diabetes.[14]

Type 1 diabetes isn't infectious, so children and teenagers can't get it from someone else or give it to companions or relatives. Furthermore, eating an excess of sugar doesn't cause type 1 diabetes, either. There's no solid method to foresee who will get type 1 diabetes, yet blood tests can discover early indications of it. These tests aren't done regularly, nonetheless, in light of the fact that specialists don't have any approach to prevent a youngster from building up the illness, regardless of whether the tests are positive.[15]

As per Diabetes Atlas distributed by the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), India was home to 62.4 million diabetics in the year 2011 and the occurrence is on a nonstop ascent and this number is anticipated to ascend to almost 70 million individuals by 2025. The nations with the biggest number of diabetic individuals will be in India, China and USA by 2030. It is assessed that each fifth individual with diabetes will be an Indian. While the ICMR study detailed that the pervasiveness was 2.1 percent in metropolitan and 1.5 percent in country zones.[11]

Knowledge of diabetes complications and prevent diabetes among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus, the degree of metabolic control is related to diabetes education of the patient or caregiver, Knowledge of diabetes complications and prevention diabetes among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus [16]. Mitchell et al.[17] found emphasized the importance of diabetes education to improve metabolic control in children and adolescents treated with CSII. The benefits of diabetes education for long-term control of adult patients with T1DM and T2DM are also avoid the complications well known.[18] We have found no studies in the literature assessing the impact of progress in knowledge of diabetes complications on the control of pediatric patients treated with MDI.

In Ireland awareness rates of ischemic heart disease and stroke among diabetic population was 89.2 and 82.8%, respectively, while that of Pakistan was 50% [19]. According to the IDF report most Ghanaians had lack of awareness about diabetic complications. Many sufferers become aware that they have diabetes, only when they develop one of its life-threatening complications. Healthcare professionals as well as public policy makers are well aware of the public health impact of diabetes. Much effort has been devoted to educate the public about diabetes through various forms of media[20].

Still in Al-Qassim region, it is not known how much the public actually know about diabetes and its associated secondary complications. The authorities will be able to decide about the need to increase the level of awareness among the non-diabetic individuals. As prevention is better than cure, awareness is always helpful to reduce the incidence of earlier onset of DM and its associated complications. This should be very helpful to reduce the additional burden of the disease to the nation, as in KSA; DM is one the major public health

issue.[21] Inordinate weight pick up is more normal during and after pubescence, particularly in young girls, just as in those with determination of diabetes in puberty. The Diabetes Control and Complications Trial and different investigations revealed expanded weight pick up as a result of serious insulin treatment with improved glycemetic control. [22]

Obese kids with type 1 diabetes have a higher pervasiveness of cardiovascular danger factors (hypertension, dyslipidemia, and heart autonomic brokenness) than typical weight youngsters with type 1 diabetes.[23] Given that ongoing information from various worldwide vaults show higher paces of overweight and heftiness in kids and teenagers with type 1 diabetes contrasted and their non-diabetic friends, cautious checking and the board of weight gain should be underscored in diabetes care as stoutness is a modifiable cardiovascular danger factor.[24]. Kids with type 1 diabetes are at expanded danger for comorbid immune system sicknesses contrasted with youngsters in everybody. Clinicians must know about the manifestations and danger factors related with normal comorbid immune system infections so that screening can be performed if there is clinical doubt for illness outside of the suggested screening stretches. A high extent of kids and young people with type 1 diabetes have distinguishable organ-explicit autoantibodies (eg, thyroid, adrenal) notwithstanding islet autoantibodies, and around 25% of patients with type 1 diabetes are determined to have another immune system disease.[25] Comorbid immune system illnesses happen all the more ordinarily in females contrasted with guys and expansion in frequency with age. In circumstances where research facility testing isn't accessible or is cost restrictive, cautious observing of straight development and significant manifestations is significant. Screening of basic comorbid conditions at standard spans, for example, immune system thyroid illness and celiac sickness, which might be subclinical or asymptomatic, allows for earlier identification and therapy.[24] In conclusion optimum management requires patient participation and cooperation to be aware of the nature of the disease and therefore decide the consequence of the illness, dimensions of treatment and its complications [22]

Rationale:

Diabetes Type 1 diabetes mellitus is a life-long disorder which can be treated by a complex regimen of insulin injections, diet and exercise, and which greatly affects the life of patients and their families. Diabetes patients may find it difficult to find medical and social support at the environment from families, staff, and other people. Consequently, this study will add significantly to the limited knowledge about the complications of diabetes among

Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus visiting the Diabetic Center. Awareness about complications and ways to prevent diabetes is very important to reduce diabetes related morbidity and mortality. As a family physician, prevention and health promotion is one of the cornerstones in our practice, thus investing in Knowledge of complications of diabetes mellitus among patients visiting the Diabetic center well fulfill the researcher aim.

Aim of the study:

This study aimed to measure the extent to which parent are Knowledge of diabetes, its complications of diabetes among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus.

Objectives:

- To measure the parents level of Knowledge of diabetes, its complications of diabetes among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus visiting the Diabetic Center at Makkah city, September 2019.

Methodology:

Study design:

This study is a cross sectional descriptive study

Study Area

The study has been carried out in the city of Makkah . Makkah is the holiest spot on Earth. It is the birth place of the Prophet Mohammad and the principal place of the pilgrims to perform Umrah and Hajj. It is located in the western area in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and called the Holy Capital. Contains a population around 1.578 million .The research has been carried at the diabetes center. There has 2 sectors in Makkah to diabetes center , one in Al-Noor Hospital, and the second in the north of Makkah.

Study Population

The study has been conducted among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus in the Diabetic Center in Al-Noor Hospital, and in the north of Makkah . During the September 2019 the period of study in 2019.

Selection criteria:

Inclusion criteria

- All type Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus who were on medication for more than 1 year and less than 18 years were included .

Exclusion criteria :

- No specific exclusion criteria.

Sample size

The sample size has been calculated by applying Raosoft sample size calculator based on (The margin of error: 5%, Confidence level: 95%, and the response distribution was considered to be 20%) accordingly the Sample size is 500 of Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus attending and adding 10 more to decrease margin of error. After adding 5% oversampling, the minimum calculated sample has been 550. Computer generated simple random sampling technique was used to select the study participants.

Sampling technique :

Systematic random sampling technique is adopted . By using systematic sampling random as dividing the total population by the required sample size; (500).

Data collection tool

Pretested structured interviewer-administered questionnaire, has been used to collect the data [26]. To serve the purpose of this study. A questionnaire of similar studies has been review . An interview Questionnaire has been uses for data collection.

- The Questionnaire has been designed in the Arabic language with a cover letter to clarify the objectives of the study and the assurance of confidentiality.
- First section: demographic data.
- Second section: questions to measure the parents Knowledge of diabetes, complications and prevention diabetes among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus

- The researcher has been examining the reliability of the questionnaire by testing and retesting.
- The questionnaire was translated to local language and then, retranslated back to English by another person to check its consistency and wording.

Data collection technique:

Researcher has been visits the selected Diabetic Center after getting the approval from the ministry of health.

After the arrival of the participants to the Diabetic Center, they should go to the reception first to register and ensure the presence of the center's card. Then, the receptionist gives to the participant's number. During that period of waiting the researcher has been a select participant conveniently until the target number achieves and gives the questionnaire for answering. She has been explained the purpose of the study to all participants attending the clinic. The data has been collect through the, 2019.

Variables of the study

Dependent variable Knowledge .

The level of knowledge of diabetes, complications of diabetes Type 1 diabetes mellitus

Independent variables.

(age, Gender Education, Economic level).

Operational definitions

DM complications presence of complications of diabetes among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus

One or more of complications on DM patients such as retinopathy, diabetic foot, renal complications, stroke, heart complications, teeth decay, neuropathy, hypertension, and sexual dysfunction [27].

Data entry and analysis:

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 24.0 has been used for data entry and analysis. Descriptive statistics (e.g., number, percentage) and analytic statistics

using to test for the association and the difference between two categorical variables were applied. A p-value ≤ 0.05 has been considered statistically significant .

Pilot study:

A pilot study has been conducted to test the methodology of the study, the questionnaire has been clear.

Ethical considerations:

Permission has been and Verbal consents from all participants in the questionnaire were obtained.

All information was kept confidential, and a result has been submitted to the department as feedback .

Relevance & Expectations:

Knowledge of complications of diabetes mellitus among patients

The researcher expects from the study, low level of knowledge of complications

Budget:

Self-funded

Results

Table 1 Distribution of demographic data(age, gender, education, economic level) in our study(n=500)

	N	%
Age		
20-40	175	35
40-60	263	52.6
More than 60	62	12.4
Range	20.5-68	
Mean±SD	44.849±12.035	
Gender		
Female	130	26
Male	370	74
Education		
Illiterate	40	8
Primary	20	4
Preparatory	50	10
Secondary	95	19
University	295	59
Economic level		
Low	120	24
Medium	225	45
High	155	31

Table 1 shows that almost of the participants parent (52.6%) were in the age group 40-60 years follow by the (35%)were in the age 20-40years and the data ranged from(20.5-68) by mean ±SD(44.849±12.035),the majority of them were males (74%) while female(26%), also Regarding the education status that almost of respondents had university educational degree

were (59%) while secondary degree were (19%). Regarding the Economic level, the majority of participants were medium (45%) while high were (31%)

Table 2 Describe the participant knowledge of information about knowledge about diabetes, knowledge about complications of diabetes of Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus

		N	%	Score	
				Range	Mean+SD
knowledge about diabetes	Weak	30	6.0	25-51	40.642+5.176
	Average	385	77.0		
	High	85	17.0		
knowledge about complications	Weak	22	4.4	9-15.	12.522+1.131
	Average	433	86.6		
	High	45	9.0		

Table 2 and Figure(1) show Regarding information of the participants toward knowledge about diabetes in the children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus study results show the data ranged from(25-51) by mean $\pm$ SD(40.642 $\pm$ 5.176) (increase in average where(77.0%) than high and weak). Regarding information of the participants toward knowledge about complications in the children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus study results show the data ranged from(9-15) by mean $\pm$ SD(12.522 $\pm$ 1.131) (increase in average where(86.6%) than high and weak.

Figure(1)Describe the participant knowledge of information about knowledge about diabetes, knowledge about complications, and knowledge about prevention diabetes of Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus

Table 3 Distribution of the knowledge about diabetes in the demographic data(age, Gender Education, Economic level) of participants toward among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus

Demographic data		N	knowledge about diabetes	F or T	ANOVA or T-test	
			Mean ± SD		Test value	P-value
Age	20-40	175	44.811 ± 1.370	F	1148.495	<0.001*
	40-60	263	40.536 ± 2.638			
	>60	62	29.323 ± 1.931			
Gender	Female	130	45.062 ± 1.451	T	13.114	<0.001*
	Male	370	39.089 ± 5.118			
Education	Illiterate	40	28.275 ± 1.569	F	874.267	<0.001*
	Primary	20	31.150 ± 0.587			
	Preparatory	50	37.040 ± 2.523			
	Secondary	95	39.737 ± 2.279			
	University	295	43.864 ± 1.602			
	Low	120	35.458 ± 4.594	F	208.323	<0.001*

Economic level	Medium	230	40.496 ± 4.424			
	High	150	45.013 ± 1.366			

Table(3) Figure(2) show that is a significant relation between knowledge about diabetes and demographic data regarding age (increase in 20-40), where $F=1148.495$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$ by mean+ SD (44.811 ± 1.370).

Regarding Gender show that is a significant relation between knowledge about diabetes and gender (increase in female), where $T=13.114$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$ by mean+ SD (45.062 ± 1.451)

Regarding the Education show that is a significant relation between knowledge about diabetes and education (increase in university), where $F=874.267$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$ by mean+ SD (43.864 ± 1.602)

Regarding the Economic level show that is a significant relation between knowledge about diabetes and economic level (increase in high), where $F=208.323$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$ by mean+ SD (45.013 ± 1.366)

Figure(2) Distribution of the knowledge about diabetes in the demographic data(age, Gender Education, Economic level) of participants toward among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus

Table 4 Distribution of the knowledge about complications of diabetes in the demographic data(age, Gender Education, Economic level) of participants toward among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus

Demographic data		N	knowledge about complications		F or T	ANOVA or T-test	
			Mean	± SD		Test value	P-value
Age	20-40	175	13.560	± 0.683	F	466.386	<0.001*
	40-60	263	12.266	± 0.692			
	>60	62	10.677	± 0.505			
Gender	Female	130	13.685	± 0.610	T	17.166	<0.001*
	Male	370	12.114	± 0.978			
Education	Illiterate	40	10.500	± 0.555	F	193.793	<0.001*
	Primary	20	11.000	± 0.000			
	Preparatory	50	11.880	± 0.627			
	Secondary	95	11.968	± 0.573			
	University	295	13.186	± 0.797			
Economic level	Low	120	11.483	± 0.830	F	266.054	<0.001*
	Medium	230	12.326	± 0.822			
	High	150	13.653	± 0.695			

Table(4) Figure(3) show that is a significant relation between knowledge about complications and demographic data regarding age (increase in 20-40), where $F=466.386$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$ by mean+ SD (13.560 ± 0.683). Regarding Gender show that is a significant relation between knowledge about complications and gender (increase in female), where $T=17.166$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$ by mean+ SD (13.685 ± 0.610)

Regarding the Education show that is a significant relation between knowledge about complications and education (increase in university education), where $F=193.793$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$ by mean+ SD (13.186 ± 0.797). Regarding the Economic level show that is a significant relation between knowledge about complications and economic level (increase in high), where $F=266.054$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$ by mean+ SD (13.653 ± 0.695).

Figure(3) Distribution of the knowledge about complications of diabetes in the demographic data(age, Gender Education, Economic level) of participants toward among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus

Discussion

Overall, the data collected and analysed indicate an decrease and lack in knowledge in Parents participating in study focused on Knowledge of diabetes, its complications of diabetes on care of children with Type 1 Diabetes . Children with diabetes type 1 (T1DM) need close monitoring for their blood glucose, food intake, insulin therapy and physical activity during day hours in order to guard.

In our study the majority of our participants were almost of the Parents (52.6%) were in the age group 40-60 years In the current study, the majority of participants were males (74%), almost of respondents had university educational degree were (59%) . (SeeTable1)

In our study the information of the participants toward knowledge about diabetes in the children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus study results show the data ranged from(25-51) by mean $\pm$ SD(40.642 $\pm$ 5.176) (increase in average where(77.0%) than high and weak). Regarding information of the participants toward knowledge about complications in the children with

Type 1 diabetes mellitus study results show the data ranged from(9-15) by mean $\pm$ SD(12.522 $\pm$ 1.131) (increase in average where(86.6%) than high and weak. Regarding information of the participants toward knowledge about prevention diabetes in the children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus study results show the data ranged from(5-14) by mean $\pm$ SD(9.356 $\pm$ 1.997) (increase in average where(62.4%) than high and weak wher22.8%).(See Table 2)

Similarly, Alnasir and Skerman (2004)[28] also found lack of knowledge of information about diabetes, knowledge about complications, and about prevention diabetes knowledge and attitudes among Bahraini schoolteachers. In Riyadh, a study conducted among primary and intermediate school compounds in Riyadh City showed that 78% of them had got fair total knowledge level. Similar results were found in the studies of Lewis et al. (2003)[29] and Melton & Henderson (2007)[30], also(Gulabani et al., 2008)[31] find in a search Diabetes mellitus, if untreated, may cause life-threatening complications . Awareness programs and

dissemination of information's can help people assess the risk of diabetes (Hoque et al., 2009).[31] In addition, it is important to motivate diabetic patients to seek proper treatment and care, and inspire them to take charge of their disease (Duckworth et al., 2009)[33]

In our study the information of the participants toward show that is a significant relation between knowledge about diabetes and demographic data regarding age, where $F=1148.495$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$, also regarding the gender show that is a significant relation between knowledge about diabetes and gender where $T=13.114$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$. Regarding the Education show that is a significant relation between knowledge about diabetes and education where $F=874.267$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$. Regarding the Economic level show that is a significant relation between knowledge about diabetes and economic level where $F=208.323$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$. (See Table 3)

Previous studies reported that DM management and care are strongly related to adequate knowledge, and there is a correlation between DM the parent's participants and demographic data [34]. A previous study in Bangladesh (2016) found that 82% of people had a basic level of DM awareness [35] , which was considerably higher than in our study. This disparity may

be explained by the previous study using the Diabetes Knowledge Test, a tool validated by the University of Michigan. Similarly, another study from Bangladesh found that 62% of the population had insufficient knowledge level about diabetes [36], which was also higher than our result. In our study the information of the participants toward show that is a significant relation between knowledge about complications and demographic data regarding age, where $F=466.386$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$. Regarding Gender show that is a significant relation between knowledge about complications and gender, where $T=17.166$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$.

Regarding the Education show that is a significant relation between knowledge about complications and education (increase in university education), where $F=193.793$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$. Regarding the Economic level show that is a significant relation between knowledge about complications and economic level, where $F=266.054$ and $P\text{-value}=0.001$. (See Table 4)

Studies have shown that the awareness about diabetes and related issues is poor in general population. Whereas in diabetic population the awareness about the diabetic complications was observed to be 50% in a study done in Pakistan.[37] In a study done by Maskey et al in Nepal also showed a male awareness more than female whereas other studies have shown a female awareness preponderance.[37] A similar study conducted in Bangladesh by haque et al had a female awareness preponderance in the study.[38]

In our study the educational status of the study population was significantly associated with awareness' of diabetic complications (P value- 0.001). In a study conducted in Shivkashi district in India it was found that 74% of the participants They have no information on complications and prevention diabetes among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus diabetic population .[39] In relation to variables associated with Knowledge of diabetes, its complications of diabetes study by Al-Maskari et al. among patients with DM reported that age, gender, and SES were related to DM knowledge, and observed a higher knowledge score among males than females ($p < 0.001$) . That study also found there was a significant difference between knowledge scores of postgraduate (19.67) and undergraduate (14.74) respondents ($p < 0.001$) [40]. Our results were consistent with that study. Similarly, a study by Islam et al. showed significant associations for all demographic variables (including DM status) with knowledge scores , similar outcomes were observed in our study. Also with similar results reported in the study in Bangladesh [41].

Conclusions

This review highlights the need for increased knowledge and awareness of Knowledge of diabetes, its complications among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus DM among the Saudi parents. The means of improving knowledge and awareness of diabetes, its complications of diabetes among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus needs to be integrated into existing healthcare systems and processes to better inform patients, families, parents and communities about this chronic disease

This systematic review highlighted the lack of knowledge and awareness of diabetes, its complications of diabetes among Children with Type 1 diabetes mellitus among the Saudi parents. To improve public knowledge and awareness, it is necessary to enhance the education

of health professionals regarding the pathology, etiologic, risk factors, management and complications of DM. A greater focus is needed on the responsibility of health professionals in educating patients, families and the community about how a healthy lifestyle can reduce the risk of developing DM and the complications of those living with this chronic disease.

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